

Impact of microbial consortia on organic maize in a temperate climate varies with environment but not with fertilization

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ABSTRACT

Inoculating crops with specifically designed microbial consortia (MC) is increasingly discussed as an instrument for sustainably promoting arable crop growth. While some promising results were achieved in laboratory, climate chamber, and greenhouse experiments, field applications of microbial inoculants under temperate climate conditions have been much less investigated. Here, we assess the effect of three novel (MC_B, MC_C, MC_C_AMF) and one commercial (Micosat F) MC in a factorial combination with three fertilization levels (unfertilized, 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹, and 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹) on organic maize (*Zea mays* L.) productivity. Split-plot experiments were performed in two consecutive years (2020 and 2021) at different locations in the Rhineland, Germany, resulting in three trial environments. The novel MC consisted of well-studied single strains of *Azotobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Burkholderia*, *Pseudomonas*, *Rahnella*, and *Glomus*. At stem elongation in 2020, crop growth (+17%), shoot nitrogen (+34%), and phosphorus uptake (+25%) were significantly enhanced upon inoculation with MC_C, possibly due to atmospheric N₂-fixation of *A. chroococcum* LS132 and phosphorus solubilization of *P. fluorescens* DR54. However, MC_C failed to impact maize productivity in 2021. This difference between years was likely due to distinct weather and pre-crop effects. Significant increases in grain yield were observed only for MC_C_AMF (+10%) in 2021. Interactions between MC inoculation and organic fertilization were not observed. Therefore, the assumption that MC are more effective in low-input systems cannot be confirmed by this study. However, the effect of fertilization on crop growth and nutrition was more common and consistent than the impact of MC inoculation in both years. As revealed by the varying performance of MC across trial environments, achieving significant, agronomically relevant, and reproducible benefits from MC inoculation still remains a considerable challenge in field-grown arable crops in temperate climate.

1. Introduction

A targeted application of beneficial microbial consortia (MC) for improvements in crop yield and quality is increasingly gaining attention in agriculture (Backer et al., 2018; Woo and Pepe, 2018; Santos et al., 2019; Saad et al., 2020; Santoyo et al., 2021). Multifunctional MC inoculants usually consist of two or more plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs). Among PGPMs, the plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) and beneficial fungi (e.g., arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) or *Trichoderma* spp.) are the most frequently used inoculants for crop growth promotion (Santoyo et al., 2021). Depending on their intended agricultural use, MC are either applied as ‘biofertilizer’,

‘biostimulant’ or ‘biopesticide’ to seeds or crops (Vessey, 2003; Du Jardin, 2015; O’Callaghan et al., 2022). Successful MC applications have been repeatedly discussed as one key factor in sustainable agricultural intensification (Gouda et al., 2018; Woo and Pepe, 2018; Aguilar-Paredes et al., 2020; Vishwakarma et al., 2020; Khan, 2022). Especially in organic farming systems with a low use of external inputs, the targeted application of MC might be an efficient tool to increase arable crop productivity. Unlike conventional intensification strategies (such as mineral fertilization or application of synthetic pesticides), inoculation with MC is assumed to increase the yield and quality of organic crops, while still preserving ecological services (Gouda et al., 2018; Vishwakarma et al., 2020). In addition, increasing mineral

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fertilizer prices, global climate change, and the necessity of ecologically sound crop production to feed a growing world population have raised the interest of conventional farmers in microbial inoculants (O'Callaghan et al., 2022).

Multiple functional mechanisms of PGPMs have been revealed (Bhattacharyya and Jha, 2012). Experiments involving different microbial single strains and MC were conducted under varying environmental conditions and in combination with diverse crops (Nadeem et al., 2014). Important beneficial microbial effects resulting in yield increases include improved plant nutrition, in particular with nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and iron (Fe), shoot and root invigoration, production of phytohormones, rhizoremediation, siderophore production, and the biocontrol of plant diseases and pests (Martínez-Viveros et al., 2010; Gouda et al., 2018). The growing interest of farmers in microbial applications and the long-time absence of a legal or regulatory definition of plant 'biostimulants' – except for plant protection purposes – have led to a continuous and fast commercialization of microbial inoculants worldwide (Hart et al., 2018; Tabacchioni et al., 2021; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). This currently burgeoning market offers a plethora of products for soil and plant inoculation. The majority of commercially available microbial inoculants primarily consist of single microbial strains inspired by, inter alia, the well-studied example of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* for soybean (*Glycine max*) inoculation (Glick, 2012; Vishwakarma et al., 2020; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). The inoculation of seeds is known to be useful when (1) the required strains are already present but the concentration of the native rhizobial population is too low and in particular, when (2) the rhizobial strains required for the symbiosis are not hosted by the soil at all. Regarding the latter case, seed inoculation of soybeans with selected *B. japonicum* strains allowed, for example, also an economically viable extension of their cultivation area to regions where the required microbial strains do not occur naturally (Catroux et al., 2001; Santos et al., 2019).

While many studies found different beneficial effects of microbial single strains under controlled environmental conditions, clear evidence of their capability to enhance crop growth under field conditions are, however, often still lacking. Experiments evaluating the performance of microorganisms under real-world scenarios (i.e., at the field level) often report inconsistent results possibly due to environmental variability. Abiotic and biotic confounders usually affect both, the biological efficacy (i.e., the power to produce significant effects) and the agronomic efficiency (i.e., the power to produce results of relevant magnitude in farming) of microbial inoculants under field conditions. Consequently, there is often still no unequivocal evidence for their utility in arable farming (Gouda et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2019; Lopes et al., 2021; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). To overcome this challenge, there is currently a growing conviction among parts of the scientific community that multifunctional MC might perform better and more reliable under changing environmental conditions in the field (Compant et al., 2019; Naamala and Smith, 2020; Vishwakarma et al., 2020; Santoyo et al., 2021; Khan, 2022; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). Major advantages of MC over single strains being often mentioned in this context include (1) a more efficient occupation of free ecological niches leading to a higher likelihood of a successful establishment, survival, and thus persistence over time; (2) the possibility of synergistic interactions and mutual assistance of the applied strains among each other and with the native soil microbiome, leading to higher and more diverse benefits than the sum of all individual parts; and (3) the possibility to ensure certain beneficial microbial effects by functionally replacing each other if specific strains do not establish under stressful conditions (Bradáčová et al., 2019; Naamala and Smith, 2020; Santoyo et al., 2021; Tabacchioni et al., 2021; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). However, exploiting the potential of MC in sustainable agricultural intensification in the future requires evidence gained in the field under different climatic conditions (Saad et al., 2020; Santoyo et al., 2021).

In this study, three new and one commercial MC were analyzed for their agronomic performance in organic maize production in temperate

climate. The novel MC were specifically composited for these trials and consisted of different well-studied microbial species, including amongst others *Azotobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Burkholderia*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Glomus* strains (Bhattacharyya and Jha, 2012; Berg et al., 2014; Woo and Pepe, 2018). Each novel MC was specifically designed to include at least one microbial strain for each of the following specific functions: (1) nitrogen fixation, (2) phosphorus solubilization, (3) amylolytic activity, (4) production of auxin or auxin-like compounds, and (5) biocontrol of pathogens (Tabacchioni et al., 2021). Initial experiments conducted under controlled environmental conditions (i.e., in a greenhouse) with antecedents of the MC evaluated here indicated a significant effect on early shoot and root growth of wheat (Hett et al., 2022). Apart from non-inoculated controls, Micosat F (CCS Aosta Srl., Quart (AO), Italy) was used as a 'positive' control in this study. For this MC, being commercially available in different countries, beneficial effects on maize growth were already reported from field experiments conducted in a Mediterranean climate (Masoero and Giovannetti, 2015; Sabia et al., 2015).

Despite a plethora of abiotic and biotic factors (amongst others e.g., host crop type, composition of microbial inoculants, soil type, and climate conditions) affecting the magnitude of microbial crop growth promotion, different meta analyses indicate a consistent overall effect size of approx. 10–20% for distinct microbial inoculants (Schmidt and Gaudin, 2018; Schütz et al., 2018; Herrmann et al., 2022). As recently shown by Schütz et al. (2018) and Herrmann et al. (2022) most evidence for arable crop growth promotion by microbial inoculants comes from countries with tropical, subtropical, and dry climates like e.g., Brazil (e.g., Hungria et al., 2010) or India (e.g., Pandey et al., 1998). Although some studies are available on microbial efficacy and efficiency from temperate climate (e.g., Mayer et al., 2010), large-scale field investigations from this climate zone with usually lower temperatures are still lacking. In particular, adequate soil temperatures during the vegetation period are known to be an important driver for soil microbial growth and activity (Pietikäinen et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2021) and thus might ultimately also affect the magnitude of microbial benefits on crop growth upon inoculation. Hence, the objective of the present study was to assess the impact of inoculating maize seeds with microbial consortia under field conditions in a temperate climate. Agronomically relevant parameters such as the vegetative growth, grain yield, total amount of aboveground biomass, plant height, and vitality as well as crop nutrient contents and uptakes were regularly assessed to evaluate and quantify the potential beneficial effects of MC inoculation on crop growth.

The hypotheses underlying this work were:

- 1) Inoculated plants outperform non-inoculated plants in vegetative growth and grain yield.
- 2) MC inoculation leads to higher crop nitrogen and phosphorus contents and uptakes.
- 3) Effects of MC on crop performance decrease with increasing fertilization rates.
- 4) MC have, at least in part, the capacity to substitute organic fertilizer.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental site and climatic conditions

Experiments were conducted on organically managed fields in three environments. In 2020, one field trial was performed at the research station for organic farming Campus Wiesengut (WG) of the University of Bonn, located in Hennef, Germany (50°47' N, 7°15' E, elevation of 64 m a.s.l.). In 2021, two field trials were conducted, one at Campus Wiesengut and another at the organic farm Wittfelder Hof (WH) located in Wachtberg, Germany (50°38' N, 7°09' E, elevation of 187 m a.s.l.). Both sites have a temperate climate (Western European-Atlantic climate) (Fig. 1), with mild winters, temperate summers, a mean annual air temperature around 10 °C (WG: 10.3 °C and WH: 9.5 °C), and relatively

Fig. 1. Air temperature [°C] and precipitation [mm] at the experimental sites in 2020 (A: Wiesengut) and 2021 (B: Wiesengut, C: Wittfelder Hof) compared with the long-term means. Soil temperature [°C] was measured at the location Wiesengut at a depth of 15 cm (D). The long-term weather data (1981–2010) for the location Wiesengut were obtained from the weather station of the German Meteorological Service at Cologne Bonn Airport (12 km distance). For the location Wittfelder Hof, the long-term data (1956–2019) were obtained from the weather station of the experimental farm Campus Klein-Altendorf in Rheinbach (12 km distance) of the University Bonn. The optimum temperature (25–30 °C) range for sufficient bacterial and fungal growth is indicated by the grey box (D) (Pietikäinen et al., 2005).

abundant annual precipitation (WG: 840 mm and WH: 640 mm). The growing season in 2020 was characterized by a dry spring and a warm summer. Compared to the long-term data (1980–2010) of this region, a precipitation deficit of > 140 mm was observed in the period from April to July 2020 (Fig. 1A). By contrast, the weather conditions in 2021 were largely defined by cooler temperatures in spring (April and May) and summer (July and August) combined with high precipitation. In July 2021, twice as much rain as in the long-term average of this region was recorded, mainly due to heavy rainfalls (> 90 mm in 24 h) on 14th July (Figs. 1B, 1C). Further important abiotic conditions like a minimum of 900 sunshine hours (Diepenbrock et al., 2005) and a temperature sum of around 1600 °C (base temperature set at 6 °C) for maize ripening were sufficiently matched in both years (2020: 1060 sunshine hours and 1824 °C; 2021: 910 sunshine hours at both sites and 1800 °C at WG and 1596 °C at WH).

The soil temperature was monitored continuously during the growing period at WG in each year. Data was collected at 15 cm soil depth using an on-farm weather station (HOBO RX3000 Station, Onset, MA, USA). Values were in line with the air temperature but had lower short-time fluctuations, ranging between 10 °C and 25 °C in both years. In 2020, the average soil temperature from 15th May to 15th September

was higher (19.8 °C) compared with 2021 (17.3 °C) (Fig. 1D).

Soil types of the trial sites were a Fluvisol (WG, in both years) and a Luvisol (WH, in 2021). Both soils have a silty-loam texture and are typical for maize cropping in Germany. The soil chemical analyses indicated a slight deficiency of Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), and Boron (B) at WG in both years. By contrast, the soil at WH was comparatively well-supplied with most macro- and micronutrients (Table 1).

2.2. Experimental design, management practices, and treatments

A split-plot design with four replications was used in all trials. Application of MC with four levels defined the main plots. Organic fertilization was assigned to the subplots with three levels (see below). Winter rye (*Secale cereale*) harvested in August 2019 followed by a cover crop of grass (*Lolium perenne*) and red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) was the pre-crop in 2020 (cultivation period: 14.08.2019 – 05.05.2020). In 2021 grass-clover was grown as pre-crop at both sites (cultivation period at WG: 14.08.2019 – 25.03.2021; cultivation period at WH: 21.08.2019 – 01.04.2021). After mulching the grass-clover, a shallow cultivation (5 cm depth) with a cultivator (WG) or a disc harrow (WH) followed in

Table 1
Chemical properties of the topsoil (0–30 cm) of the experimental fields.

Location		pH (CaCl ₂)	P	K	Mg	Na	Fe	Cu	Mn	Zn	B	TOC ^c	TN ^d
		ppm ^b											
		%											
Wiesengut	Value	5.4	20	20	60	< 2	220	6.9	248	11	< 0.1	0.93	0.10
2020	Level ^a	B	A	A	C	A	–	E	E	E	A	–	–
Wiesengut	Value	5.8	60	40	70	6	300	7.6	232	15	0.1	1.20	0.12
2021	Level	B	B	B	C	B	–	E	E	E	A	–	–
Wittfelder Hof	Value	6.1	150	140	140	2	757	4.9	128	18	0.9	1.26	0.17
2021	Level	B	C	C	D	A	–	E	E	E	C	–	–

^a Regional supply levels for Germany according to the classification of the German Chamber of Agriculture: A = very low, B = low, C = normal, D = high, E = very high, “–” = not available; ^b Parts per million; ^c Total organic carbon; ^d Total nitrogen content.

all years before primary tillage was done with a moldboard plow (23 cm depth) in the first week of May. The seedbed was prepared with a rotary harrow one day before sowing. Maize (*Zea mays* L., cv. Benedictio) seeds were sown manually in 2020 on 7th May and in 2021 using a precision drilling machine on 12th (WG) and 13th (WH) May. The sowing dates were adjusted to the soil temperature, i.e., to provide favorable starting conditions for the MC inoculants, sowing was not performed before soil temperatures had reached 12 °C in 15 cm depth (Nguyen et al., 2019). In both years, the sowing depth was 5–6 cm. The row distance was 75 cm and the sowing density was ten seeds per m². Individual plots had a net size of 10 m x 3 m and consisted of four rows. One machine width (i.e., four rows) of non-inoculated maize was sown as buffer between all main plots to avoid cross-contamination among the microbial treatments. To minimize bird damage, the trials were covered with nets up to growth stage (BBCH) 14. Due to severe drought at sowing, maize plants were irrigated in 2020 during germination (BBCH 13–16). In total, 45 mm water split into three parts was applied to the sowing band. To minimize interspecific competition with weeds, uniform mechanical hoeing and manual weeding was carried out several times during the growing season in all plots. No agrochemicals (e.g., synthetic fertilizer or pesticides) were applied in any of the trials.

2.2.1. Microbial consortia production and crop inoculation

In this study, three recently developed MC (MC_B, MC_C, and MC_C.AMF) and one commercially established MC (Micosat F, CCS Aosta Srl. (Aosta, Italy); Masoero and Giovannetti, 2015; Sabia et al., 2015) were evaluated in field trials. Microbial consortia B and C consisted of five different bacterial strains, while MC_C.AMF was further supplied with a mixture of six different AMF strains provided by CCS Aosta Srl. The commercial MC Micosat F is based on ten different microbial strains (Table 2). In 2020, non-inoculated controls (CON), MC_B, MC_C, and Micosat F were investigated, while MC_B was replaced by MC_C.AMF in 2021. This adjustment was done based on the results obtained in 2020. The main idea of this type of streamlining was to make the most promising novel MC even more effective and resilient by further supplying it with AMF.

The identification and selection process of microbial strains for MC formulation, their functional characteristics and modes of action, and their compatibility to co-exist were described in detail by Tabacchioni et al. (2021). While cultivation of single strains and preparation of MC were in 2020 performed following the methods described by Hett et al. (2022), small modifications were made in 2021 and MC production was done as reported in Magarelli et al. (2022). Since the final quality check after stabilization revealed no differences in the colony forming units

Table 2
Specific composition of the microbial consortia (MC) used in the experiments. The concentration of each individual active member in zeolite is given as colony forming unit (CFU) or spores per gram after stabilization.

Microbial Strain	Microbial consortium (MC)				Quality check (spores or CFU ^a g ⁻¹)	
	MC_B	MC_C	MC_C.AMF	Micosat F	2020	2021
	<i>Azotobacter vinelandii</i> DSM2289	X				1.90 * 10 ⁷
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. BV84	X				4.00 * 10 ⁶	–
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> LMG9814	X	X	X		3.95 * 10 ⁶	7.34 * 10 ⁷
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> DR54	X	X	X		5.00 * 10 ⁶	1.00 * 10 ⁶
<i>Rahnella aquatilis</i> BB23/T3d	X	X	X		7.00 * 10 ⁵	1.00 * 10 ⁶
<i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i> LS132		X	X		2.80 * 10 ⁷	1.50 * 10 ⁷
<i>Burkholderia ambifaria</i> MCI7		X	X		3.00 * 10 ³	1.00 * 10 ⁴
<i>Acaulospora morrowiae</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Gigaspora gigantea</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Gigaspora rosea</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Glomus mosseae</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Scutellospora pellucida</i>			X		–	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> TH01				X	≥ 3 * 10 ⁵	≥ 3 * 10 ⁵
<i>Glomus mosseae</i> GP11				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Glomus coronatum</i> GU53				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Glomus caledonium</i> GM24				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Septoglomus viscosum</i> GC41				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i> RI31				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> BA41				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> PA29				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> AB86				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷
<i>Komagataella pastoris</i> PP59				X	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷	≥ 6.5 * 10 ⁷

^a colony forming unit.

(CFU) (see Table 2) between both years, it is assumed that the adjustments in the production method had no impact on microbial viability and quality. Both production cycles are described in brief below.

In 2020, in the first step, single strains were picked up from cryopreserved pure cultures stored at -80°C in 30% glycerol and grown in liquid nutrient broth (NB, Oxoid Limited, Hampshire, United Kingdom). Flasks were incubated at 200 rpm and 28°C for 24–72 h depending on the requirements of the specific strain. Production took place in two identical cycles with three replicates, respectively. Purity and cell density were checked for each strain using the surface-viable count method (Miles et al., 1938). After centrifugation and resuspension in sterile water and prior to stabilization in zeolite (i.e., the carrier), a final minimum concentration of 10^9 CFU per mL was ensured for all individual strains. Stabilization was achieved by mixing 100 mL liquid culture suspension of centrifuged and resuspended strains with 1 kg of sterile micronized zeolite (grain size distribution $< 75\ \mu\text{m}$). Formulation of MC was done by adding all single strains in a 1:1 ratio. For quality control, 24 h after stabilization, the cell density was checked by resuspension of the powder (i.e., of with microbial strains formulated zeolite) in sterile water followed by serial dilution and plating of the suspension (Table 2).

In 2021, the growth of microbial single strains was performed in a pilot scale bioreactor according to the protocol described by Magarelli et al. (2022). In brief, a loop of each bacterial strain was picked up from cryopreserved pure cultures stored at -80°C in 30% glycerol and streaked onto nutrient agar (NA, Sigma-Aldrich, Milan, Italy) plates. After checking purity, strains were grown overnight in Nutrient Broth (NB, Sigma-Aldrich, Milan, Italy) at 26°C and 130 rpm. Then flasks (100 mL) were inoculated with each bacterial strain by adding 100 μL of overnight grown cultures and incubated at 26°C and 130 rpm for 24 h in a thermostatic orbital shaker (Thermo Scientific Forma, model 420, Dreieich, Germany). To scale up the production process, each bacterial strain was grown in NB in submerged cultures in a 21-L stirred-tank bioreactor (B. Braun Biotech International, Berlin, Germany). After 36 h the microbial biomass was dehydrated by freeze-drying for each bacterial strain. Stabilization in 2021 was done in analogy to 2020, i.e., by mixing the final (lyophilized) strains with zeolite as carrier. Comparable to 2020, 24 h after stabilization, the cell density was checked by resuspending the zeolite (formulated with the specific microbial strains) in sterile water followed by serial dilution and plating of the suspension (Table 2).

Microbial consortia were applied twice during the growing season. Initially, untreated maize seeds were coated with MC using an organic seed binder (SEBI-B5, Globachem, Sint-Truiden, Belgium). Wetted seeds were mixed with the MC powder and carefully shaken to ensure a sufficient adhesion. Surplus MC were removed by sieving. Using this technique, averaged over all MC applied, approx. 0.15 g of MC as powder were attached per seed corresponding to a total application rate of $15\ \text{kg}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$. The second application was carried out one week prior to the expected anthesis (BBCH 65) in each year. Re-inoculation was done using application quantities of ca. $15\ \text{kg}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$. Applied MC had the same spore and hyphae concentrations as used for seed inoculation. Field spreading of MC dispersed in water was done using watering cans (10 L per 10 m row). Control plants were treated with pure zeolite at the same total application rate as for MC (i.e., $15\ \text{kg}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$).

2.2.2. Organic fertilization with potato protein liquid

To assess the applied MC under contrasting nutrient supply levels, fertilization was performed with potato protein liquid (PPL) (Bollmer Holding GmbH, Wietmarschen, Germany). The amount of fertilizer was adjusted depending on the availability of mineral nitrogen (N_{min} in $\text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$) in the topsoil at stem elongation in each year (Suppl. Table 1). Fertilization was split up into three levels including: (0) soil level without fertilization, (1) moderate fertilization, and (2) intensive fertilization (Suppl. Table 2). For moderate fertilization of plots in 2020 a total of $56\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WG) and in 2021 either $4\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WG) or

$38\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WH) were applied. These amounts were chosen to reach the target value of $110\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$, in combination of applied fertilizer and measured stock of available nitrogen. Likewise, in 2020, $146\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WG) and in 2021 either $94\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WG) or $128\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$ (WH) were applied in intensively fertilized plots to achieve a total of $200\ \text{kg}\ \text{N}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$, consisting of the amount of soil mineral nitrogen and the added fertilizer. Potato protein liquid is a complete organic fertilizer with high nutrient contents (weight percent: 2.2% N, 1.2% P_2O_5 , 7% K_2O , 0.5% MgO, and 0.7% S). Fertilization was performed at BBCH 35 and PPL was specifically mixed with water in order to apply an equal quantity of liquid to each row (10 L) of all plots. To minimize the competition of maize plants for nutrients, fertilization was extended over the four core rows to two additional rows at each border. Control plots were treated with water (10 L per row).

2.3. Data collection and measurements

To assess crop vigor by the means of the leaf spectral reflectance, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, Eq. 1, Rouse et al., 1974) was measured at the upper three leaves using a handheld spectrophotometer (Polypen RP 410 UVIS, Photon Systems Instruments, Drásov, Czech Republic). Plant length was measured from the soil surface to the plant tip using a folding rule. Stem diameter was quantified directly below the first node with a digital caliper. The non-destructive measurements were carried out at stem elongation, anthesis, and ripening with ten measurements per plot using different plants.

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{R_{\text{NIR}} - R_{\text{RED}}}{R_{\text{NIR}} + R_{\text{RED}}} \quad (1)$$

Above-ground biomass samples were harvested and chemically analyzed at two dates per vegetation period. First, plant samples were collected at stem elongation (BBCH 38) on $2.0\ \text{m}^2$ per plot. To analyze the yield structure, a second sample was taken at maturity (BBCH 90) on $3.0\ \text{m}^2$ per plot and portioned into grains, cobs, and stover. For the biomass analyses, plant aerial parts were cut approx. 10 cm above soil, separated, shredded, oven-dried at 60°C for 24 h and at 105°C until constant weight. Dry-matter samples were ground in a vibratory disc mill (RS200, Retsch® GmbH, Haan, Germany) for 90 s at 1400 rpm. Milled samples were used for the chemical analysis of the crop N and P contents. Plant N was assessed using an elemental analyzer (EURO-EA3000, Eurovector, Pavia, Italy) upon chemical pulping of 4 mg shoot biomass with acetanilide. After microwave digestion of ca. 200 mg milled material at 220°C for 30 min with the use of 4 mL conc. H_2O_2 and 6 mL conc. HNO_3 , P was measured photometrically at 880 nm with the molybdenum blue method using a continuous flow autoanalyzer (QuAatro39, SEAL Analytical, Southampton, UK). Nutrient uptake ($\text{kg}\ \text{ha}^{-1}$) was determined by multiplying plant dry weights and nutrient contents.

2.4. Statistical evaluation

Data analysis was performed using the open-source software R (version 4.1.2) with RStudio (version 2021.09.2) (R Core Team, 2021). A linear mixed-model (*lmer* function) fit by Restricted Maximum Likelihood (ReML) and Satterthwaite's method was developed, applied to all agronomic parameters, and used for the calculation of a multi-factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA) for each response variable. A Type II ANOVA was calculated and the Kenward-Roger method was applied for the determination of the correct denominator degrees of freedom. In a first step, the agronomic results were jointly analyzed for all three environments (i.e., all combinations of experimental site and year). Second, due to statistical interactions, data analysis was performed separately for each year based on the different compositions of the tested MC, the distinct climatic conditions, and the varying pre-crop effects in both years.

Application of MC (main-plot factor), organic fertilization (sub-plot

factor), and experimental location (only in 2021) were defined as fixed factors in the model. In 2021, both trials were jointly analyzed whenever possible, depending on significance of interactions between site and trial factors. Akaike's Information Criterion (Burnham et al., 2011) was used to select the most parsimonious statistical model for each response variable. Homogeneity of variances was checked with a plot of residuals versus fitted values. Normal distribution of residuals was visually assessed with a normal quantile-quantile (QQ) plot (Kozak and Piepho, 2018). If necessary to meet the above-mentioned criteria, the data was transformed to its square root or logarithm (log₁₀). Untransformed data are presented. After ANOVA and where applicable, mean values of treatments were compared using the Tukey-test at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Unless further specified, results are shown as the mean of four replications and standard deviations were included where suitable.

3. Results

Maize plants showed a vigorous growth and homogenous development in all three trials. During the vegetation period, crops remained healthy and neither phytosanitary problems with pests, diseases or weeds nor relevant abiotic growth constraints apart from the drought in 2020 were noticed. Environmental conditions allowed a fast growth in both years and resulted in an above-average yield compared to the yields obtained in the national maize variety trials of the German Chamber of Agriculture (Mücke, 2022).

3.1. Crop development and NDVI

Significant microbial effects on crop development and plant vitality were only observed in 2020 at later crop developmental stages (Table 3). At anthesis, plants treated with MC_C achieved a crop length of 224 cm that was significantly higher compared to all other treatments (+8%). At the same time, plant robustness and vitality measured indirectly by the NDVI were also significantly enhanced in plants inoculated with MC_C when compared with Micosat F, but not compared with the control. In addition, especially in terms of plant height and NDVI, a strong impact of fertilization in 2020 and the experimental location in 2021 was observed. These effects were clearly stronger than the benefits caused by MC (Table 3). In 2021, neither fertilization nor MC inoculation had an

effect on plant height or stem diameter (Table 3).

3.2. Maize biomass production and yield formation

Maize growth was only in one experimental season (2020) and only by one of the two novel MC (MC_C) significantly enhanced at stem elongation (BBCH 38) (Fig. 2). Inoculation with MC_C induced a significant increase in shoot dry weights in 2020 compared to all other microbial treatments (+19%) and compared to the non-inoculated control (+17%). Micosat F achieved higher shoot dry weights compared to the novel MC_B but did not differ from non-inoculated controls. While achieving an early growth-advantage in 2020, MC_C failed to positively affect maize growth at stem elongation in 2021 at both experimental sites. The efficacy and efficiency of all evaluated MC in promoting vegetative maize growth was strongly affected by the experimental site in 2021. At the location Wittfelder Hof, maize growth was not affected by MC inoculation. By contrast, at the experimental site Wiesengut, application of MC_C_AMF (7.5 t dm ha⁻¹) and Micosat F (7.5 t dm ha⁻¹) resulted in a significantly higher maize shoot biomass compared to plants inoculated with MC_C (6.1 t dm ha⁻¹) but not compared to non-inoculated ones (6.2 t dm ha⁻¹) (Fig. 2). Intensive fertilization with PPL significantly increased vegetative maize growth in 2020 (+20%), but not in 2021.

The microbial-induced plant growth-promotional effects observed at stem elongation were partially found also in selected treatments at maturity (2020: MC_C and 2021: MC_C_AMF; see Table 4 and Fig. 3). However, for most agronomic parameters assessed at harvest (e.g., stover, spindle, and total plant biomass, thousand grain weight, and harvest index), only a moderate trend but no significant increase was observed (Table 4). Beneficial microbial effects were most apparent with regard to the significantly increased grain yields per cob in both experimental seasons. Inoculation with MC_C resulted in a significantly higher (+15%) grain yield per cob in 2020 and MC_C_AMF led to a significant increase of 9% in 2021 compared to the non-inoculated control. While no MC significantly affected maize grain yield in 2020, MC_C_AMF inoculation achieved a significantly higher grain yield (+10%) compared to non-inoculated controls in 2021 (Table 4). Maize productivity and especially grain yield differed strongly between both years and was considerably higher in 2021 than in 2020 (+27%).

Table 3

Maize plant height [cm], stem diameter [mm], and leaf spectral reflectance (NDVI) measured at different plant developmental stages and affected by application of microbial consortia (MC), fertilization (unfertilized plots (0); plots fertilized at 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (1); plots fertilized at 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (2)), and experimental location in 2020 (Wiesengut) and 2021 (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof). Ten individual plants were evaluated per plot. Data show the mean of four replications. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences. ANOVA with Tukey-Test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Year	Treatment	Plant height [cm]			Stem diameter [mm]			Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI)		
		Stem elongation	Anthesis	Ripening	Stem elongation	Anthesis	Ripening	Stem elongation	Anthesis	Ripening
2020	Microbial consortium									
	Control	154	208 b	208 ab	18.9	18.4	17.5	0.6663	0.6536 ab	0.6436
	MC_B	146	207 b	206 b	20.1	19.2	18.3	0.6665	0.6521 ab	0.6549
	MC_C	163	224 a	223 a	19.9	19.8	19.2	0.6713	0.6664 a	0.6549
	Micosat F	154	209 b	213 ab	19.7	19.2	18.5	0.6656	0.6484 b	0.6466
	Fertilization									
	0	152	204 b	204 b	19.9	19.1	18.2	0.6597 c	0.6348 c	0.6315 b
	1	155	214 a	215 a	19.6	19.1	18.7	0.6682 b	0.6593 b	0.6550 a
	2	156	218 a	218 a	19.5	19.3	18.2	0.6744 a	0.6712 a	0.6635 a
2021	Microbial consortium									
	Control	164	295	295	24.8	22.3	22.3	0.6340	0.6484	0.6434
	MC_C	164	291	290	24.5	21.6	21.4	0.6331	0.6435	0.6367
	MC_C_AMF	167	292	293	24.3	21.9	21.6	0.6341	0.6475	0.6375
	Micosat F	170	296	296	24.7	22.0	22.0	0.6341	0.6470	0.6395
	Fertilization									
	0	167	292	291	24.6	22.2	21.7	0.6340	0.6461	0.6368 b
	1	167	294	295	24.8	22.0	22.1	0.6347	0.6467	0.6395 ab
	2	165	294	294	24.4	21.7	21.6	0.6328	0.6470	0.6415 a
	Location									
	Wittfelder Hof	181 a	306 a	305 a	25.6 a	24.2 a	23.7 a	0.6332	0.6382 b	0.6255 b
	Wiesengut	152 b	281 b	282 b	23.6 b	19.7 b	19.8 b	0.6344	0.6550 a	0.6530 a

Fig. 2. Maize shoot biomass [t dm ha⁻¹] at stem elongation as affected by the application of microbial consortia (MC) and fertilization (unfertilized plots (0); plots fertilized at 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (1); plots fertilized at 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (2)) in 2020 (A and B) and by MC application and experimental location (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof) in 2021 (C and D). Red squares indicate the arithmetic mean of four replications. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences. ANOVA with Tukey-Test at $\alpha = 0.05$. dm = dry matter with 0% moisture.

In contrast to microbial inoculation, organic fertilization with PPL had a significant impact on all evaluated yield parameters in 2020, including grain yield, stover yield, spindle yield, total biomass production, grain yield per cob, thousand grain weight, and harvest index (Table 4). Plots with intensive fertilization produced a total plant biomass that was on average 24% higher than in the unfertilized control. Likewise, grain yield (+34%), grain yield per cob (+33%), and thousand grain weight (+11%) were significantly enhanced. In contrast to MC inoculation, fertilization with PPL also increased the harvest index and thus the contribution of the grain yield to the total biomass. Unlike in 2020 where moderate fertilization also achieved a significant differentiation from unfertilized plots, only intense fertilization evoked significant increases in 2021. Though achieving smaller differences than in 2020, the total biomass production (+5%), grain yield (+6%), and grain yield per cob (+6%) were still significantly increased by intensive PPL fertilization compared to unfertilized plots in 2021.

Hence, while in 2020 the effect size of PPL on vegetative growth (BBCH 38) and generative yield (BBCH 90) was clearly higher than the impact of MC inoculation, the overall magnitude and the difference in the effect size between both experimental factors on crop growth were

much lower in 2021 (Fig. 3). In addition, in case that a beneficial impact of MC on crop growth was observed, this effect was in both years for most MC greater at stem elongation (BBCH 38) than at maturity (BBCH 90).

3.3. Crop nitrogen and phosphorus contents and uptake

Maize shoot nutrient contents (%) and uptake rates (kg ha⁻¹) were significantly affected by MC application at stem elongation in 2020 (Table 5). Shoot N and P contents were significantly higher compared to those of the non-inoculated controls but neither differed from MC_B nor from Micosat F. Likewise, shoot nutrient uptake of N (+34%) and P (+25%) of plants inoculated with MC_C was significantly enhanced compared to all other treatments (Table 5). Fertilization with PPL led to a gradation with higher N and P uptake rates in moderately and highly fertilized plots in 2020. By contrast, in 2021, neither MC inoculation nor PPL fertilization significantly affected maize shoot nutrient contents and uptake at stem elongation (Table 5).

Although significant microbial-mediated plant nutritional benefits were observed at least at stem elongation (BBCH 38) in 2020, maize

Table 4

Maize yield structure at maturity as affected by the application of microbial consortia (MC), fertilization (unfertilized plots (0); plots fertilized at 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (1); plots fertilized at 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (2)), and experimental location in 2020 (Wiesengut) and 2021 (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof). Data show the mean of four replications. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences. ANOVA with Tukey-Test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Year	Treatment	Yield structure						
		Stover [t dm ^a ha ⁻¹]	Spindle [t dm ha ⁻¹]	Grain [t dm ha ⁻¹]	Total biomass [t dm ha ⁻¹]	Grain yield per cob [g dm]	TGW ^b [g dm]	HI ^c [-]
2020	Microbial consortium							
	Control	6.5	1.7	10.1	18.2	98.3 b	252.5	0.551
	MC_B	6.3	1.7	9.9	17.9	104.2 ab	260.1	0.555
	MC_C	7.1	1.9	10.8	19.8	112.7 a	268.8	0.545
	Micosat F	6.4	1.6	9.7	17.7	108.8 ab	266.4	0.546
	Fertilization							
	0	6.1 b	1.6 c	8.5 c	16.1 b	90.2 c	244.5 b	0.529 b
	1	7.0 a	1.7 b	10.4 b	19.2 a	108.1 b	269.5 a	0.547 b
	2	6.7 ab	1.9 a	11.4 a	20.0 a	119.7 a	271.9 a	0.572 a
	2021	Microbial consortium						
Control		9.2	2.2	12.3 b	23.7	109.6 b	217.7	0.522
MC_C		9.1	2.2	12.7 ab	24.1	113.9 ab	196.6	0.529
MC_C_AMF		9.8	2.4	13.5 a	25.8	119.9 a	200.5	0.525
Micosat F		9.6	2.3	12.9 ab	24.8	115.4 ab	210.7	0.521
Fertilization								
0		9.2	2.3	12.6 b	24.1 b	111.5 b	201.7	0.522
1		9.4	2.3	12.8 ab	24.4 ab	114.7 ab	208.2	0.525
2		9.7	2.3	13.3 a	25.3 a	117.9 a	209.2	0.526
Location								
Wittfelder Hof	10.2 a	2.3	12.9	25.4 a	117.3 a	204.6	0.508 b	
Wiesengut	8.6 b	2.3	12.9	23.8 b	112.1 b	208.1	0.541 a	

^a dm = dry matter with 0% moisture,

^b Thousand grain weight,

^c Harvest index.

Fig. 3. Effect size (%) of microbial consortia (MC) inoculation and potato protein liquid fertilization on maize growth and nitrogen (N) uptake at stem elongation (BBCH 38) and on maize grain yield and total N uptake at maturity (BBCH 90) compared to non-inoculated and unfertilized plants, respectively. Data for the experimental season 2020 refer to one trial (Wiesengut), while the data for the experimental season 2021 refer to two trials (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof). The controls (i.e., non-inoculated plants and unfertilized plots) were set as one hundred percent and thus correspond to the coordinate origin. The absolute data of the controls are given in the [supplementary Table 3](#).

nutrient supply at harvest (BBCH 90) was neither in 2020 nor in 2021 affected by MC inoculation (Table 6). Unlike the non-significant microbial trends for higher grain and total nutrient uptakes observed for MC_C in 2020 and MC_C_AMF in 2021, PPL fertilization significantly affected crop nutrient contents and uptakes of different plant parts at

maturity in both years (Table 6). In all trial environments, highest N contents and uptakes were observed for maize stover, grain, and total biomass in the intensively fertilized plots. Fertilization increased grain N content by 19% and 6% in 2020 and 2021, respectively. Higher maize N contents were also accompanied by significantly higher grain (2020:

Table 5

Shoot nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) content (%) and uptake (kg ha⁻¹) at stem elongation (BBCH 38) as affected by the application of microbial consortia (MC), fertilization (unfertilized plots (0); plots fertilized at 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (1); plots fertilized at 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (2)), and experimental location in 2020 (Wiesengut) and 2021 (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof). Data show the mean of four replications. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences. ANOVA with Tukey-Test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Year	Treatment	Nutrient content [%]		Nutrient uptake [kg ha ⁻¹]	
		N	P	N	P
2020	Microbial consortium				
	Control	1.87 b	0.29 b	56.9 b	8.7 b
	MC_B	2.12 ab	0.30 ab	60.6 b	8.5 b
	MC_C	2.18 a	0.31 a	76.1 a	10.9 a
	Micosat F	2.04 ab	0.30 ab	63.4 b	9.2 b
	Fertilization				
	0	1.89 b	0.30	54.4 c	8.5 c
	1	2.09 a	0.30	63.1 b	9.1 b
	2	2.18 a	0.30	75.2 a	10.5 a
	2021	Microbial consortium			
Control		2.17	0.34	139.8	22.0
MC_C		2.07	0.34	133.2	22.2
MC_C_AMF		2.13	0.35	152.3	24.8
Micosat F		2.05	0.34	147.3	24.2
Fertilization					
0		2.03	0.35	139.5	24.2
1		2.11	0.34	146.8	23.9
2		2.17	0.33	143.1	21.9
Location					
Wittfelder Hof	2.03 b	0.39 a	138.2	26.4 a	
Wiesengut	2.18 a	0.30 b	148.1	20.2 b	

+59%; 2021: +12%) and total N uptake rates (2020: +59%; 2021: +13%) in both years. In line with the results observed for crop growth, the total effect size of PPL fertilization on shoot N uptake at stem elongation (BBCH 38) and total plant N uptake at maturity (BBCH 90) was at least in 2020 clearly higher than the effect size of MC inoculation (Fig. 3). Significant differences between both experimental sites were not observed in 2021.

Compared to N, plant P contents showed a reverse trend. Despite

Table 6

Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) content (%) and uptake (kg ha⁻¹) of maize stover, spindle, and grains at maturity as affected by application of microbial consortia (MC), fertilization (unfertilized plots (0); plots fertilized at 110 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (1); plots fertilized at 200 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ (2)), and experimental location in 2020 (Wiesengut) and 2021 (Wiesengut; Wittfelder Hof). Data show the mean of four replications. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences. ANOVA with Tukey-Test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Year	Treatment	Nutrient content [%]						Nutrient uptake [kg ha ⁻¹]							
		Stover		Spindle		Grain		Stover		Spindle		Grain		Total	
		N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P
2020	Microbial consortium														
	Control	0.67	0.18	0.44	0.13	1.18	0.29	44.1	11.8	7.2	2.2	120.6	28.5	171.9	42.5
	MC_B	0.84	0.17	0.49	0.13	1.23	0.28	54.0	10.3	8.4	2.2	124.2	27.7	186.6	40.2
	MC_C	0.78	0.17	0.43	0.12	1.24	0.28	55.6	12.1	8.3	2.3	134.1	30.4	198.0	44.8
	Micosat F	0.74	0.18	0.39	0.13	1.21	0.29	48.5	11.7	6.4	2.0	117.5	27.5	172.4	41.2
	Fertilization														
	0	0.59 b	0.21 a	0.45	0.14 a	1.11 c	0.31 a	35.7 b	12.7 a	7.0	2.2	94.8 c	26.5 b	137.5 c	41.4
	1	0.78 a	0.16 b	0.46	0.13 b	1.21 b	0.29 b	56.0 a	11.5 ab	7.9	2.2	126.9 b	30.4 a	190.8 b	44.1
	2	0.89 a	0.15 b	0.41	0.12 c	1.32 a	0.25 c	59.9 a	10.2 b	7.9	2.2	150.6 a	28.6 ab	218.4 a	41.0
	2021	Microbial consortium													
Control		0.80	0.20	0.38	0.12	1.22	0.26	74.3	18.6	8.4	2.7	150.9	32.5	233.6	53.8
MC_C		0.82	0.23	0.32	0.12	1.21	0.26	75.5	22.0	7.2	2.7	154.1	33.7	236.8	58.4
MC_C_AMF		0.81	0.22	0.34	0.12	1.22	0.26	80.0	22.0	8.2	2.9	165.4	35.5	253.6	60.4
Micosat F		0.81	0.22	0.37	0.13	1.23	0.27	77.6	21.7	8.4	2.9	159.3	34.8	245.3	59.4
Fertilization															
0		0.77 b	0.24 a	0.35	0.12	1.19 b	0.27	71.9 b	22.6	8.1	2.8	149.6 b	33.6	229.6 b	59.0
1		0.78 b	0.21 ab	0.35	0.12	1.22 b	0.26	74.0 b	20.4	7.9	2.7	155.8 b	33.6	237.7 b	56.7
2		0.87 a	0.20 b	0.35	0.12	1.26 a	0.27	84.5 a	20.2	8.1	2.8	166.9 a	35.2	259.5 a	58.2
Location															
Wittfelder Hof	0.84 a	0.28 a	0.39 a	0.13 a	1.23 a	0.31 a	86.1 a	29.1 a	8.9 a	3.0 a	159.3	39.9 a	254.3 a	72.0 a	
Wiesengut	0.78 b	0.15 b	0.31 b	0.11 b	1.21 b	0.22 b	67.6 b	13.0 b	7.2 b	2.5 b	155.5	28.4 b	230.3 b	43.9 b	

higher P loads in intensively fertilized plots, maize stover, spindle, and grain P contents were in part significantly higher in unfertilized plots compared to the fertilized ones (Table 6). This dilution effect was consistently observed in both years, independent of the soil P supply level. In addition, in 2021 a strong and significant impact of the experimental location on the P content and uptake was observed. Stover, spindle, and grain P supply were higher for plants grown at the location ‘Wittfelder Hof’ compared to the location ‘Wiesengut’.

4. Discussion

4.1. Impact of fertilization and environment on maize growth and MC performance

Crop inoculation with novel MC and PPL fertilization in part significantly affected crop growth, yield, and nutrition under temperate climatic conditions. However, the growth-promoting effect of fertilization was more pronounced and consistent than the impact of MC inoculation (Fig. 3). Potato protein liquid, the condensed liquid residue of the potato starch-processing industry, is usually produced at high temperatures. This leads to high amounts of readily plant available nutrients in the applied liquid. As confirmed in this study, PPL significantly improves crop growth and nutrition already within the year of application (Möller and Schultheiß, 2015). Although PPL was just shortly applied before the first biomass sampling was done (i.e., ca. 10 days in advance), it already significantly affected the NDVI (Table 3), shoot biomass (Fig. 2), shoot N content, and shoot N and P uptake (Table 5) in 2020. Comparing both experimental years, maize growth was more often affected by one or both experimental factors in 2020 than in 2021. In detail, in 2020 fertilization significantly affected 26 out of 35 investigated agronomic parameters (2021: ten out of 35), while MC inoculation had a significant impact only on nine out of 35 parameters (2021: three out of 35).

Particularly the beneficial pre-effects of grass-clover explain the higher crop productivity level observed in 2021 (e.g., +27% grain yield). Forage legume mixtures like red clover and grass are usually characterized by the efficient symbiotic N₂-fixation from the atmosphere. In contrast to winter rye being the pre-crop in 2020, grass-clover

mixtures leave large quantities of shoot and root residues, i.e. N, after harvest on the field for the subsequent crop (Watson et al., 2002). This well-known effect increasing the soil fertility in terms of a higher N availability was confirmed by different soil N_{\min} contents at stem elongation in this study. The soil N_{\min} in 2020 was only approx. half as large as in 2021 (Suppl. Table 1). However, this inherent increase in soil N fertility left probably less space for further growth improvements by MC inoculation or fertilization in maize cropping in 2021 (Fig. 2 and Table 4). Likewise, more favorable climatic conditions (Fig. 1) with sufficient precipitation (amount and distribution) boosted soil nutritional dynamics in 2021 and provided more appropriate growth conditions than in 2020.

Interactions between MC inoculation and fertilization were not identified in any trial environment. Therefore, the hypothesis that MC are particularly effective under low-input conditions cannot be confirmed by the results obtained in this study. As shown by two meta-analyses (Schmidt and Gaudin, 2018; Schütz et al., 2018) and two recently published reviews (Lopes et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2021), the effect of low or high nutrient contents on microbial efficacy and efficiency is still inconclusive for many microbial species. While several studies report no interaction between microbial inoculation and fertilization or even an improved nutrient utilization if fertilizer is applied together with MC or crops are inoculated in soils with high nutrient contents (Thonar et al., 2017; Di Salvo et al., 2018; Vinci et al., 2018; Mpanga et al., 2019; Galindo et al., 2022), others showed that beneficial microbial effects were masked or superimposed with increasing fertilization rates and/or soil fertility levels (Ozturk et al., 2003; Shaharouna et al., 2008; Krey et al., 2011; Nguyen et al., 2019; Hett et al., 2022). Despite the absence of a significant interaction between fertilization and MC inoculation in our study, especially in 2020, the highest microbial effects were observed in the unfertilized plots at stem elongation (BBCH38) and maturity (BBCH90). Shoot dry weight (+27%), shoot N content (+28%), shoot N uptake (+62%), grain yield (+25%), total biomass yield (+22%), and grain N uptake (+33%) were at least one fifth higher in plants inoculated with MC_C compared to non-inoculated ones. In 2021, a better performance of MC in unfertilized plots was neither noted at stem elongation nor maturity. This observation is most likely related to the higher soil fertility (i.e., nutrient contents) of the whole field (see Table 1 and Suppl. Table 1). However, considering that PPL fertilization was conducted in both years to achieve a comparable nitrogen supply, there are possibly further factors apart from a higher soil N fertility that have led to the different performance of MC in both experimental seasons.

The absence of significant effects and thus a limited reproducibility of beneficial microbial effects under field conditions between two consecutive years was also reported by Nguyen et al. (2019) using different *Bacillus* strains in wheat production under temperate climatic conditions. Functionally, the reasons for the absence of beneficial microbial effects are often multifarious, difficult to specify, and hard to investigate under field conditions using a targeted experimental design due to several interacting environmental conditions. Constraints limiting both the effectiveness and efficiency of microbial inoculants include biotic and host-related factors on the one hand (e.g., host specificity, root colonization, plant-microbe signaling, and microbial competition) and abiotic and soil-related factors (e.g., soil fertility, soil temperature, soil moisture, and soil pH) on the other hand (Khare and Arora, 2014; Shah et al., 2021).

Regarding the abiotic constraints, low soil temperatures are assumed to be a key factor affecting microbial efficacy and efficiency in temperate climate (Nguyen et al., 2019). The majority of PGPMs currently discussed for agricultural purposes belong to the group of mesophilic microorganisms (e.g., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Azotobacter* spp., or *Glomus* spp.). These PGPMs usually have an optimal growth rate and highest functional activity at temperatures around 25–30 °C or even higher (Pietikäinen et al., 2005; Aasfar et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021). However, as shown in Fig. 1, such soil temperatures are exceptional in

temperate climate. Pandey et al. (1998), identified this temperature constraint to be the major reason for a limited microbial efficacy, efficiency, and reproducibility under temperate climate compared to subtropical climate.

4.2. Differences between microbial consortia in their effects on maize productivity

Based on the growth conditions described above, the significant effect of MC_C on early crop growth (Fig. 2) and nutrition (Table 5) observed in 2020 is supposed to be caused at least in part by the additional N provided by MC inoculation. Improvements in crop N nutrition (content: +17% and uptake +34%) are assumed to be primarily caused by the diazotrophic bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum*. Associative N_2 -fixation is known to be one of the key-factors by which *A. chroococcum* promotes crop growth (Wani et al., 2016; Tabacchioni et al., 2021). However, compared to symbiotic N_2 -fixation by *Rhizobia* (50–465 kg N $ha^{-1} a^{-1}$), the total amount of N provided by *Azotobacter* species is by far lower (Pankievicz et al., 2019). It often ranges only between ca. 15–20 kg N $ha^{-1} a^{-1}$ (Kizilkaya, 2009; Saha et al., 2017; Pankievicz et al., 2019). Hence, the significant additional N uptake observed at stem elongation in 2020 (+19.2 kg N ha^{-1}) upon MC_C inoculation is consistent with the magnitude reported in the literature for *A. chroococcum*. Improved maize growth (vegetative and generative) and nutrition were also reported in other field studies using either different *A. chroococcum* single strains (Pandey et al., 1998; Zahir et al., 2005; Gholami et al., 2012) or MC supplied with further microbial strains (Zahir et al., 1998; Umeha et al., 2014). Under subtropical conditions, Pandey et al. (1998) observed a significant and more than twofold increase in grain and total biomass yield, N content, and uptake upon maize seed inoculation with *A. chroococcum* W5. However, as also reported by the authors, the same strain failed to significantly affect crop growth under temperate conditions. This result is in accordance with our observations at maturity (Table 6).

The similarity of MC_C and MC_B (only two strains differ, see Table 2) and the failure of MC_B to affect crop growth suggest that the superior performance of MC_C may have been caused by a higher performance of *A. chroococcum* LS132 compared to *A. vinelandii* DSM2289. Despite a similar, but non-significant trend in improved plant nutrition neither vegetative nor generative crop growth was significantly enhanced by MC_B inoculated plants (Fig. 2 and Table 4). However, this failure of MC_B to affect maize growth under field conditions contradicts its earlier observed capacity to enhance early wheat growth and N nutrition in pot experiments (Hett et al., 2022). This observation illustrates that proofs of microbial efficacy and efficiency in more controlled environments such as pot experiments remain an important and necessary, but still insufficient pre-condition for their practical use in farming. Nonetheless, this finding also suggests that the plant growth-promotional effects of MC_C might not be exclusively attributed to a nitrogen effect. Important functional mechanisms of *A. chroococcum* other than atmospheric N_2 -fixation promoting shoot invigoration include e.g., the production of phytohormones (auxins, cytokinins, and gibberellic acid-like substances) and vitamins, the secretion of antibacterial and antifungal substances and siderophores, and phosphorus solubilization (Pandey et al., 1998; Kumar et al., 2001; Mrkovacki and Milic, 2001; Viscardi et al., 2016; Wani et al., 2016). In addition, the positive effects of MC_C on early maize growth observed in 2020 might be also partly explained by the presence of *Burkholderia ambifaria* MCI7 in this MC (see Table 2). This specific strain has already been proven in different greenhouse experiments to enhance early maize growth (Bevino et al., 2000; Ciccillo et al., 2002).

However, the significant increase in shoot P content (+7%) and uptake (+25%) observed in this study at stem elongation for MC_C in 2020 might not only be provided by *A. chroococcum* but also by other components of the MC. In particular, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, being part of all evaluated MC (Table 2), is known to enhance crop P nutrition by

different functional mechanisms (Oteino et al., 2015). In pot experiments conducted under semi-field conditions, *P. fluorescens* DR54 being part of MC_C was shown to significantly enhance the activity of distinct soil phosphatases (acid, alkaline, and phosphodiesterase) at early maize and oilseed rape growth stages (Krey et al., 2011). Especially under unfertilized conditions, this increased enzyme activity enhanced the amount of highly soluble P pools in the soil (e.g., +10% water-soluble P) and thus the amount of directly plant-available P. Ultimately, these microbially-mediated benefits were in part also translated into a higher maize growth, nutrient uptake, and yields comparable to the size observed in this study (Krey et al., 2013a, 2013b). In addition to P solubilization and mobilization, the application of *P. fluorescens* DR54 was further accompanied by a strong and significant promotion of maize root colonization by soil-indigenous AMF (up to +248%) (Krey et al., 2011, 2013a, 2013b). Likewise, a targeted application of, e.g., *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* FZB45 with or without further organic or mineral P and N fertilizer was proven to enhance maize growth and P content and uptake in different trials (Vinci et al., 2018; Mpanga et al., 2019, 2020). Differences in the efficacy of MC inoculation and fertilization as well as the impact of the experimental location on crop P nutrition observed in this study (Table 5 and Table 6) are likely affected by different soil P supply levels (Table 1). The soil P₂O₅ supply measured in calcium acetate lactate solution was 3–7.5 times higher in 2021 (WH: 150 ppm and WG: 60 ppm) than in 2020 (WG: 20 ppm). Lower P supply levels at WG compared to WH are probably due to long-term pig-keeping at the latter.

Despite achieving potentially agronomically relevant results at stem elongation in 2020, this study also demonstrated clearly the current obstacles to using beneficial MC in field agriculture. The two major challenges were (1) that even though significant growth-advantages of inoculated plants were detected at early growth stages, these were not necessarily translated into significantly higher yields at maturity and (2) that the reproducibility of beneficial effects on crop growth and nutrition provided by the same MC was weak between both years (Fig. 3). While MC_C significantly affected maize growth in 2020, the same MC failed to impact crop growth in 2021 unless further supplied with AMF (Fig. 2 and Table 4). Given the overall low and mostly inconsistent performance of the MC tested in this study, no meaningful answer to the question of whether MC inoculation can, at least in part, substitute organic fertilizer from the results obtained in this study. The capability of other PGPMs to act as a fertilizer equivalent is, for example, already well-known for different rhizobia-based inoculants in legume cultivation (Santos et al., 2019).

Based on the observation that only MC_C-AMF significantly improved grain yield in 2021, but MC_C alone did not, it is assumed that the improved growth is related to AMF. As natural root symbionts, the key mechanism by which AMF improve host growth and yield in both stressed and non-stressed environments is the provision of plants with inorganic nutrients and water (Begum et al., 2019). The improvements in crop nutrition observed after MC inoculation in 2021 only tended to be higher but were not significant. Further microbially-mediated plant growth-promotional effects not directly assessed in this study (e.g., phytohormone or siderophore production) are assumed to have also affected plant growth and yield (Martínez-Viveros et al., 2010; Begum et al., 2019).

4.3. Towards a more critical assessment of microbial inoculation effects in arable farming

Although rarely reported in the scientific literature, a complete failure of different microbial inoculants in improving crop growth and yield is assumed to occur quite often in field experiments (Bashan et al., 2020; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). Trends for an increased crop growth not supported by statistical evidence as observed in this study (2020: MC_C; 2021: MC_C-AMF) were also reported for field-grown maize inoculated with the commercial MC 'Effective Microorganisms®' (Megali et al., 2015). In an overview study, Mayer et al. (2010) intensively studied the

impact of 'Effective Microorganisms®' on crop growth under temperate climatic conditions. Using a 4-year field experiment including crop rotation of potato, barley, lucerne, and wheat, the authors did not observe any significant improvements, neither in arable crop yields nor in soil quality parameters. Independent of a significant vegetative growth effect observed in other studies, the ultimate absence of a significant impact of Micosat F on maize grain yield production, as observed in this study, was also reported from other field trials (Masoero and Giovannetti, 2015; Sabia et al., 2015; Tripaldi et al., 2017). However, reliable grain yield increases are likely to be of crucial importance to convince farmers to use microbial products.

A partial absence of agronomic benefits and especially the limited reproducibility of microbial effects is not only evident in field applications but also in greenhouse and laboratory experiments (Gouda et al., 2018; O'Callaghan et al., 2022). Instability and inconsistency in microbial performance have led to a pronounced criticism of the commercialization of microbial inoculants. In particular, it is argued that the presumed importance of MC in field agriculture might often not be in line with the contemporary scientific knowledge obtained from independent research (Hart et al., 2018; Ryan and Graham, 2018; Kaminsky et al., 2019). Based on the results achieved in this study, the first and second hypothesis cannot be consistently confirmed. Inoculated crops showed neither a general improvement of growth and yield over non-inoculated crops, nor achieved reproducible and consistent improvements in crop nutrition. Given this inconsistent performance of MC under field conditions, crop inoculation with the microbes evaluated here cannot be recommended as an agricultural management approach to increase organic arable crop productivity. If PGPMs are still regarded as a potential strategy for a more sustainable agricultural production, multi-environment field experiments with a focus on agronomically relevant parameters (e.g., crop health and yield) are essential. This will inevitably imply also more decentralized on-farm research to evaluate microbial efficacy and efficiency in a larger number of contrasting environments (i.e., in different soil types, climatic locations, crops, etc.). Such experiments will provide further urgently required information on their reliability, effect size, and thus overall agronomic utility. To this end, it is necessary to develop a manual for routine testing of PGPMs that provides uniform criteria for the evaluation and definition of acceptable efficacy levels.

Apart from the presence or absence of agronomically relevant effects on crop growth and nutrition, tracing the fate of microbial inoculants in soils after application is essential for the functional explanation of results. Monitoring MC is of particular importance because the soil ecosystem of healthy agricultural soils usually acts like a buffer against artificially introduced microbiota (van Veen et al., 1997). In the past years, innovative analytical methods, e.g., the omics-based approaches and the next generation sequencing, have led to a better understanding of plant-microbe interactions. The availability of such methods continuously promotes the decryption of individual contributions of single strains in MC (Khan, 2022). However, due to high costs, large-scale field evaluations of microbial inoculants with these novel methods are still rare. Nevertheless, following the fate of PGPMs in agricultural soil is important for a reliable use of microbial inoculants in sustainable agricultural production.

5. Conclusion

Our work indicates that specifically selected microbial inoculants with different functional properties are in part able to improve maize growth, nutrition, and yield. Observed increases in vegetative crop growth and nutrient uptake of plants inoculated with MC_C in 2020 are assumed to be primarily related to an improved N and P supply provided by *A. chroococcum* and *P. fluorescens*. By contrast, significantly higher grain yields observed in 2021 for MC_C-AMF, but not MC_C, may be attributable to a more efficient nutrient acquisition by AMF. However, as shown by the varying performance of the same MC in two consecutive

years, it still remains a considerable challenge to achieve significant, agronomically relevant, and reproducible benefits from microbial inoculations. Potential reasons for a limited MC performance in arable crop production might be connected to soil fertility and in particular to soil temperatures in temperate climate. To achieve a clearer insight into the driving factors currently limiting microbial application in field agriculture, interdisciplinary research is needed focusing on the biological efficacy and the agronomic efficiency of MC on the one hand and on functional changes in soil microbiology including the establishment, persistence, and migration of introduced MC on the other hand. As ‘one-fits all’ solutions cannot be expected in this area, future research should focus on the identification of suitable environmental conditions under which a successful use of microbial inoculants can be expected.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jonas Hett: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Thomas F. Döring:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Annamaria Bevivino:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Daniel Neuhoff:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Dr. Daniel Neuhoff reports financial support was provided by European Commission.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.eja.2023.126743](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2023.126743).

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